

老家“LAO JIA”

By

Vivian Ji

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A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

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Approved by:

Date:

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Professor Wendy Grieb

Professor Garrett Kaida

5/31/2022

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Director University Honors Program

About the Artist

Vivian Ji is a Chinese-American background designer based in Los Angeles, California. She will be receiving her Bachelor of Fine Arts with a concentration in Entertainment Art/Animation from California State University, Fullerton. During her time at CSUF, Vivian was heavily involved with the Pencil Mileage Club—the University's largest art club—and Associated Students Inc. She was the Historian (2019-2020), Event Coordinator (2020-2021), and eventually President (2021-2022) for PMC. At ASI, she worked as an Art Workshop Instructor before transitioning into a Graphic Design position. Vivian aspires to be a background designer and eventually an art director for television animation.

Senior Honors Project Mentor

For my Senior Honors Project titled *老家* "Lao Jia," I worked alongside full-time Animation faculty member Wendy Grieb and part-time Illustration faculty member Garrett Kaida. I began this project in Garrett's 483C course and continued to work on it with constructive feedback from both Wendy and Garrett.

Goals of the Project

老家 "Lao Jia" revolves around the creation of a visual development package intended for use in a children's TV series cartoon. It is meant to supplement Vivian's

digital portfolio while showcasing her cultural roots and pursuit of diversity in the TV animation realm.

Cultural Significance

This project is an homage to Vivian's cultural roots and in particular, her paternal heritage. In Shanghai, her grandparents and father endured the Cultural Revolution of Mao China. Vivian took this opportunity to learn about the upbringing and struggles of her paternal family. The world and characters in *老家 "Lao Jia"* reflect some of her family's rural lifestyle before immigrating to the United States.

Premise

老家 "Lao Jia" takes place in rural Shanghai in the beginning of the early twentieth century. The story follows the eldest daughter of the Zhang (张) family, Xiu Lan, as her and her family navigate the hardships of a snowy winter. Everyone in the family comes together and does their part to nurse Xiu Lan's younger brother, Xiu Ming, back to health.

Ultimately, this is a story about the importance of familial kinship and blood bonds. Families may be small units in the grand scheme of society, but their role in raising and nurturing future generations is essential.

老家 “Lao Jia” Artwork

